

VALKYRIES

D2.5 Harmonization framework M12

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1. Executive Summary

WP2 provides the design, specifications, and requirements that need to be taken into account throughout the project life cycle. This includes an in-depth review of system requirements, out comes from consultations with stakeholders, and pre-standardization research.

The Deliverable 2.5 *Harmonization framework* presents the VALKYRIES methodology for agile harmonization and standardization. It will be dynamically updated based on its effectiveness, conducted corrections, and related opportunities discovered.

This deliverable is the first harmonization framework report. There will be a second one at the end of the project.

The harmonization and standardization process is a multidisciplinary process where cross-sectoral experts with heterogeneous knowledge shall contribute, providing support in multiple initiatives, such as literature identification, specific procedures (and their differences between regions/countries), evaluation and information exchange.

2. Identification

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3. Introduction

Since the beginning of time, natural and man-made events have caused innumerable victims, damage to the environment, and the economy that disturb the life of the society where it impacts. With technological evolution, a threat has been added to the historical ones, generating an increase in risks. This makes it necessary to generate a greater and better environment of security and protection for the entire society. This translates into carrying out actions executed in a planned and collaborative manner among all the agents involved to minimize the impact, especially the social and psychological impact, as well as reducing the vulnerability of the community to the consequences of disasters through the Disaster Management Lifecycle: Mitigation, Preparedness, Response, Recovery, and Toward Disaster Resilience.

Figure 1 - Valkyries global vision

Faced with these needs, the European Commission (EC) as a supranational figure has established structures to develop Pan-European resilience against disasters.

- Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre (DRMKC)¹
 - This tool integrates existing scientific interdisciplinary knowledge and co-develops innovative solutions according to needs. The activities developed translate and analyse complex scientific data.
 - INFORM. Collaboration of the Inter-Agency Standing Committee Reference Group on Risk, Early Warning and Preparedness and the European Commission.

¹ [Home - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](http://Home - European Commission (europa.eu))

- Risk Data Hub. Web platform of European wide risk data and methodologies for Disaster Risk Assessment.
- DRM Networks.
- Social Media-Driven Disaster Risk Management (SMDRM). Identify, understand, and address the challenges for improving adoption of non-traditional social media data for disaster management by taking a collaborative approach between researchers and practitioners in disaster management to co-design solutions.
- Global Conflict Risk Index (GCRI). Expresses the statistical risk of violent conflict in a given country in the coming 1-4 years and is exclusively based on quantitative indicators from open sources.
- Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources (EIOS). A unified, multidisciplinary approach to early detection, assessment and communication of public health risk using publicly available information.
- Unión Civil Protection Knowledge Network². Based on three principles or pillars: Partnership, Knowledge and Innovation. Partnership serves as a portal that promotes the transfer of knowledge and technology through scientific networks. Knowledge acquired by the lessons learned and exercises for the improvement of the results as scientific methods. Innovation composed of learning, development and verification through tests and trials.
 - Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEM). Information for emergency response and disaster risk management.
 - Union Civil Protection Mechanisms (UCPM).

The European framework presents special interest in the great risks at the border and those of low risk and great impact. These tools help in risk management and a response developed under the responsibility of the Member States (MS) that supports a joint response strategy.

Valkyries explores and analyses current and cutting-edge technologies, standards and regulations that have an impact on emergency management in border locations and that support the collaboration of security forces and volunteers from the countries involved and within the European Community. Based on this objective, methodologies, adaptation tactics and criteria are developed for the harmonization of Pan-European systems. The solutions that will be generated are:

- SIGRUN: Reference integration based on requirements and needs highlighted by end users and participants of the Consortium.
- KARA: Block intended for technologies and equipment
- HERJA: Procedures and operations
- EIR: Collaboration and training

Disasters require rapid adoption to the circumstances. They differ widely from a closed process in which all the inputs and outputs of the process are known. Therefore, a standard methodology is not the same as in other areas and a more agile process is required.

² [About - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://european-commission.europa.eu)

3.1. OODA Cycle - Introduction

The appearance of disasters and emergencies can have a natural origin that is difficult to detect beforehand, either due to natural or man-made causes. These challenges are constant in the military environment, for this reason the OODA decision-making tool was born and developed, since it was created by Colonel John Boyd of the United States Air Force based on his experience in combat and training of pilots. VALKYRIES uses OODA as a decision-making tool in uncertain and chaotic environments in a combined framework of harmonization and validation. It presents a dynamic continuous improvement cycle applicable to any business area and its characteristic is rapid decision-making when a problem appears on the horizon, allowing the use of the latest technological advances as solutions.

OODA tool is applied directly to command and control, which it could be a process, a tool, or a device that executes four basic tasks sequentially and repetitively: observation or data collection, elaboration of information or orientation, then taking or it helps to make a decision and in the end it is executed or acted upon. The treatment of command and control together with the OODA tool is to try to prevent, modify or interfere with the OODA cycle causing any disaster, for example, an electromagnetic countermeasure or a computer virus. According to Boyd, the success of the tool will be greater the faster its OODA cycle is completed, since it means a greater update, it adapts better to the environment and/or present adversities, cancelling their effect. To achieve success, the least possible friction must be pursued internally, that is, between all the participants in the tasks at each stage of the cycle. For this, it is a requirement that everyone has perfect knowledge of the objectives of leadership and the alignment of each participant with this and the objectives set. This shared vision guarantees coherence between strategy, operations and tasks that are carried out to achieve the objectives³.

Figure 2 - OODA loop

OODA is made up of four phases that continuously within an identified context, both internal and external, and dynamic, which works continuously, updating the result for optimal decision-making at all times.

- Observation: Deep acquisition of knowledge and preliminary information.
- Orientation: Through data analysis, the best hypothetical approximation is reached to address the gaps discovered and materialize the opportunities.

³ <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/download/articulo/4604097.pdf>

- Decision: Selection of the most appropriate harmonization path and it is applied within the integration.
- Action: Display, evaluate and contrast the assumed hypothesis based on the analysis of the information.

3.2. OODA vs popular continuous improvement tools

Over the years, overcoming obstacles in a global and dynamic environment, it has created a multitude of decision-making tools and continuous improvement tools that help achieve success and the best solutions in all kinds of activities.

Some of the most popular decision-making tools are SWOT analysis, Pareto diagrams, decision tree, Ishikawa diagram, or the recent Big Data. Each one presents some characteristics. Ishikawa diagram or fish tail shows the possible causes of a specific event so that by solving the root cause a problem can be solved. The decision tree is a flowchart that illustrates the results of different options in the form of a tree. Big Data uses a huge amount of data that, after analysis, generates results to facilitate decision-making.

On the other hand, the best-known continuous improvement tools are PDCA, EFQM or Six Sigma. They are methodologies that seek to achieve better and better results continuously using parallel techniques.

OODA presents some benefits:

- Quick and simple decision-making without the need for iterative elaboration of a complete cycle like other continuous improvement tools
- To provide transparency between organizations and awareness of the context by having a constant review process in all phases and among all participants.
- Greater agility in the review of all phases of the improvement cycle allows for continuous improvement and immediate correction of deviations, maintaining an optimal level in the quality of the output of the processes.
- Dynamic behaviour of each of the phases compared to other continuous improvement methodologies, because traditionally the analysis is done on a consolidated or stable photo while the OODA tool works dynamically analysing different hypotheses and generating adapted solutions.
- To work in environments with low certainty.

4. Objectives

The main objective of the deliverable is to expose the harmonisation framework applied in Valkyries. In order to do so, it is necessary to understand the needs of the project, of a cross-border disaster and the specific need. Finally, the methodology will be adapted to the process by developing a framework.

The secondary objectives of this framework harmonization are:

- Aligning harmonisation requirements with the project
- Aligning project needs with the harmonisation methodology

5. OODA protocol

Valkyries' global vision encompasses four main levels of action inspired by the OODA cycle under a combined framework of harmonization and validation. For the transfer of the OODA concept to Valkyries. Observation with the acquisition of previous knowledge and information will be identified (gaps and opportunities will be identified between regulatory frameworks, international, national and local standards, as well as operational procedures. Will be accounted the needs of the different stakeholders. A map of opportunities for first aid and those innovations of any nature with high disruptive potential will be integrated into it.). Orient will be the reasons for the best hypothetical approaches to address the identified gaps and realize the opportunities (a harmonization framework will be established taking into account the regulatory implications on certain reference models and creating / adapting established and selected criteria among existing standards). Decide stage consists of selecting the most appropriate harmonization pathways and applying them to a reference integration (some of them will be technologies and equipment, capacity for interoperability, collaboration and training, and the development of procedures and operations). Finally, Act consists of deploying, evaluating and confirming the assumed hypothesis based on analytical and empirical results (assumed criteria will be confirmed. Border demonstrations are carried out for verification and validation under an evaluation methodology. Also, field notes and recommendations will be recognised).

Figure 3 - Valkyries OODA loop

The VALKYRIES Consortium hypothesis on potential OODA under the following core statements:

Fast and efficient reaction against disruptions and non-EU pre-standardisation actions. The OODA tool stands as suitable for any business in terms of quick decision-making in the face of any upcoming external challenge to maintain an optimal response to any event. It is of special interest with the appearance of new technological and computer solutions and those initiatives born from sharing information and online experience between entities of different nature and location but covered by common objectives.

Harmonisation supported by Divergent and Future Thinking mechanism. Convergent thinking consists of giving a specific solution to a specific problem, on the other hand, divergent thinking analyses the situation to assess different options and execute the optimal one or the one with the highest value in a complementary way, future thinking tries to analyse the possible changes in the future between various variable parameters. This unique conjunction within a multidisciplinary commission of experts allows the generation of different scenarios and hypotheses to achieve the optimal ones via a convergence of possible alternatives within a context of high variability or uncertainty.

Flexibility, usability and most effective stakeholder engagement. A feature of the OODA loop is the ability to generate small OODA loops that work towards a larger purpose. These small OODAs can converge aided by standardization and normalization by different groups and sources of information while dynamically impacting other OODAs. It is characteristic to have cycles that overlap in time and objective to reach the optimum, since the source of information and objectives are reviewed, under certain hypotheses.

Speed-up and agile rational-comprehensive decision-making. Taking solutions for major crises involves analysing the vertical and horizontal implications and their consequences at all levels, from the strategic to the field operation.

It is necessary to carry out a harmonization taking into account their ability to adapt, time and economic resources involved from their decision to deployment. The OODA-based approach tries to provide continuous flexibility in decision-making.

Deployable and applicable at capability thorough development life cycle. The harmonization through OODA developed by Valkyries allows obtaining EMS solutions from design, integration and validation. This generates a tool for obtaining other solutions in the future and adapting them to the European market under the highest-level standards and adapted to the identified needs and requirements.

The lack of harmonization and inefficient regulation represent a high cost in international initiatives. Any technological change, the appearance of new and unique solutions, pose a challenge in the face of the difficulties of cross-border, between different sectors and different hierarchy operation. This is observed when supervising compliance with regulatory requirements and the application framework for cross-border operations, requiring a high effort to comply.

The purpose and objective of the harmonization is to create, comply with and validate a methodology based on the OODA for rapid and efficient response to the appearance of novel technological solutions by the first responders related to emerging technologies, procedures and collaborative environments. Carrying out decision-making in a rational manner under the convergent-divergent function and future thinking will allow adaptation to the particularities of the different sectors involved, transversal operation, usefulness and acceptance of the stakeholders involved in the harmonization process. The methodology will take into account all the relevant areas such as the political, economic, military, social, business, health, among others, and their possible combinations between them to analyse the final impact on all of them and on the final solution. To achieve success, various use cases will be developed where gaps and opportunities will have been identified to carry out a reference integration to generate guidelines, field notes and lessons learned as a result.

6. Valkyries information flows

The Valkyries organisation chart defines a relationship between the different work packages.

Valkyries is composed of seven work packages:

Work package 1 is the operational and technical project management part of the project with contractual, financial, legal, technical, ethical and administrative components. It also aims at securing the work plan, decision-making, technical coordination, data management and quality assurance support it.

The work package 2 provides specifications and requirements to be taken into account in the project life cycle. It provides a common frame of reference. This work package guides the rest of the project. From the task requirements, the harmonisation methodology to the overarching architecture.

Work package 3 defines the Valkyries ecosystem. In ethical-legal and societal terms. This work package guides the rest of the project: from ethical-legal aspects, to data protection, standards and certification.

On the other hand, the technological work packages. These work packages are the ones that will concentrate the more technical work to provide more inputs and outputs to the project system.

- WP4: Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses
- WP5: Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses
- WP6: Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses

The work package 7 represents the integration reference in the platform (SIGRUM). Also in the evaluation and demonstration through the use cases. Tests will be carried out on what has been provided in the project in this final stage.

Each work package produces inputs and outputs that affect other work packages.

Work packages have needs (inputs) that must be solved by others producing a guideline or recommendation (output). This process within work packages occurs with OODA loops.

6.1. OODA protocol in Valkyries tasks

In the following “Figure 4 - Valkyries information flows” can be see the requirement relationships of the work packages

Figure 4 - Valkyries information flows

To explain how this works, we will explain an OODA cycle for a sample task within each of the harmonisation processes.

Task: Technological work packages do not know how to manage patient information in accordance with data protection.

Observe: The need for first responders is observed.

Orient: The decision process is oriented

Decide: The most appropriate option for managing the data is decided.

Act: The output is provided to the other work package

7. OODA protocol in Valkyries harmonization process

As discussed above, the more OODA cycles are run and the faster they are run, the better the result.

Therefore, the OODA cycle should contain simple problem solving. These problems should contain little information with few inputs and outputs so that they can be solved quickly. Large needs are broken down into small problems in order to quickly make decisions.

These small decisions are framed within the processes within each project task.

Each of the project tasks follows the defined harmonisation process in which first information is gathered, then gaps and commonalities are detected and finally suggestions or improvements are produced. Finally, the output of each task together with the other tasks and the synergies between them form the output of the project

Just as information flowed through the tasks and from there to the work packages, internal decisions are made within the tasks. The sum of these small steps produces the harmonisation process, which is one of the steps of harmonisation.

7.1. Valkyries harmonization process

Figure 5 - Valkyries harmonisation process

To explain how this works, we will explain an OODA cycle for a sample task within each of the harmonisation processes.

Existing state of the art

In this first stage of the harmonisation process, the state of the art is analysed. It identifies needs and applicable legislation and procedures. For each time information is obtained and when it is filtered, an OODA loop is carried out.

One of the many OODA loops that occurs within this stage:

Task: I need to map the operational processes of first responders.

Observe: I observe, identify first responders that may have procedures and are open for consultation for the project.

Orient: I target my search for first responders who are within the scope of the project and who are willing to collaborate.

Decide: I decide on the consultation I am going to carry out.

Act: I launch the consultation on their operational procedures.

Gaps and commonalities identification

This is the second stage of the harmonisation process. In this stage, based on the identified state of the art, gaps and commonalities are sought. Gaps can be identified between the requirements and needs of the first responders and what we currently have. Gaps can also be identified between the different procedures of the emergency responders. For each of the gaps identified, an OODA cycle was carried out.

One of the many OODA loops that occurs within this stage:

Task: Identify gaps and commonalities by comparing operational procedures.

Observe: I observe the operational procedures

Orient: I orient my decision on the gaps and commonalities that the procedures appear to have.

Decide: I decide what is a gap or a commonality.

Act: I report that gap

Suggestion and improvements

Based on the gaps identified, opportunities may arise to solve the problem. This is the last phase in which opportunities for improvement occur. For each of the identified gaps the task leader carries out an OODA cycle.

Task: Identify opportunities for improvement based on the gaps identified.

Observe: I observe the identified gap(s) and their relationship.

Orient: I orientate the possible solution that these gaps may have.

Decide: I decide which opportunity is most appropriate.

Act: I report the opportunity.

8. Ongoing harmonization's

Based on the OODA cycle and the examples given. The project will propose future harmonisation on the opportunities that seem most promising. The analysis of these opportunities is more clearly explained in the deliverables and documents that specifically address them.

8.1. WP3 - Responsible innovation, certification and exploitation

OPP: Minimum data Set

Why: There is a gap in cross-institutional and cross-border information share during the emergency. The data to be shared during the emergency and a classification of this data is not defined which makes it difficult to share.

How: Based on the Ulstein-Style, a method will be developed to agree on the minimum data during the emergency and a categorisation will be proposed. Resulting in a harmonisation on the minimum set of data to be shared during the emergency.

8.2. WP4 - Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses

OPP: Location of near/nearest vehicles

Why: The main problem in a collaboration scenario between emergency services from different countries is that it is hard to be effective by coordinating their fleet of vehicles and mobile assets to manage the incident due to the lack of mechanisms to share information.

How: There are some useful mechanisms and standards which are already implemented to cover this problematic, for example, Fleet Management System (FMS), Fleet Engine API from Google, and AWS IoT FleetWise from Amazon.

OPP: Cross border data trace

Why: Part of the data gathered in emergency scenarios must comply with a series of laws and regulations. As consequence, sharing data between countries requires a common agreement and ruling of how and when that data sharing process can be done.

How: Establishing and defining a data registration models schema to record the agreements and political authorizations. Therefore, it can allow to trace the shared data using which cross border agreement.

OPP: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges

Why: There is excessive use of non-digital communication in systems used in healthcare. For example, data management and decision-making lie in professionals who, despite being experts, can choose wrong decisions. Hence, intelligent artificial is crucial to provide more accurate solutions.

How: Digitation of first responders' action can reduce the dependency on voice communications, as well as automating many information flows, allowing to collect data obtained more efficiently.

OPP: Use of wearables to support triage

Why: The use of wearable devices could speed up the triage process, therefore skilled personnel can focus on the most serious victims.

How: Automation and artificial intelligent could process data gathered from wearables used in triage to obtain triage status, allowing to support victim prioritisation.

OPP: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

Why: Learning from history events occurred in previous disasters allow to predict previous trends.

How: The use of intelligence artificial such as machine learning allows to generate trained models which can be used for predicting events that happened in the past. Consequently, these models are used to calculate potential risks and develop better plans for disaster managements.

8.3. WP5 - Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses

OPP: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

Why: Those involved in emergency planning, preparedness and response use specific terms that are not always harmonised. In cross-border disasters, the fact that intervening agencies do not use the same terminology and semantics can lead to confusion.

How: Through a unified glossary and mapping of joint terminologies and semantic representations focusing on the specificities of cross-sectoral, cross-border and hierarchical response to European multi-casualty disasters.

OPP: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

Why: Not all information transmitted by data or voice during an emergency is considered essential for a coordinated and efficient response. Sometimes information is provided that is not relevant at a particular time during the emergency or, conversely, information that is considered vital for decision making is not provided.

How: Establish a Minimum Data Set (MDS) that includes all the basic information needed to support the coordinated action of the main agencies and organisations involved in the first response to mass casualty incidents and disasters. This MDS will be developed on the basis of consensus between first responders and experts.

OPP: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

Why: There is great heterogeneity in command-and-control procedures and systems in EU countries. In situations where several agencies, territories or countries have to coordinate in response to an MCI or disaster, a common federated system for information sharing would be very useful.

How: First responders and experts will discuss which systems should be integrated into a common platform to enable information sharing in emergency response.

OPP: Harmonization of emergency response plans

Why: Responding to MCIs and disasters, especially those of a cross-border nature, requires the coordination of the agencies involved in the affected territories. This coordination would be facilitated if the agencies could consult the information considered relevant to the management of the incident.

How: Register including fields of information considered relevant to emergency management from the point of view of first responders and emergency managers. This information will be cross-checked by experts.

OPP: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

Why: For the triage of victims in MCI and disasters, different triage methods exist. Each emergency service, depending on its procedures, uses one or the other. In situations where services from different countries work together, it can be misleading not to work with the same triage method, as the same colours or priorities are not applied.

How: A proposal is made for unified triage priorities and triage labelling codes in such situations based on literature.

OPP: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

Why: There are also differences in emergency alert and warning procedures. It would be desirable to harmonise the criteria for alerts and warnings through a common EU model.

How: It is proposed to establish the METHANE model as a common EU model for early warning information in MCI and disasters.

8.4. WP6 - Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses**OPP: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data**

Why: The main problem regarding the mechanisms to provide data confidentiality relies in their computational capabilities. This includes the capabilities required to encrypt the data, to decrypt the data and the capabilities necessary to venerate a certain cryptosystem.

How: Application of light cryptographic mechanisms that can be used during the emergency actuations; §Encrypt the data within the database; Use secure protocols such as HTTPS for data transmission.

OPP: Creation of Virtual Operation Support Teams

Why: Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs) can provide helpful information to governmental structures and/or local authorities about additional resources available to support the regularly alerted responders. At the same time, a VOST would be able to identify needs expressed in the respective social networks in order to support the responsible crisis team in decision-making or prioritisation.

How: The establishment VOSTs during the UCs implementation will be based of the lessons learned from some EU MS. They will help authorities manage information in high-pressure information environments. These teams will monitor social media, improve situational awareness, counter rumours and disseminate official

communication. Establishing this kind of teams within the EU MS will improve cooperation among different first responders in the field.

OPP: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

Why: This training will lead to a better understanding of the possibilities for joint action in planning, preparing and responding to emergencies resulting from mass-casualty cross-border MCI.

How: Development and testing of training program and scenario for joint multinational training of civil-military teams in case of MCI.

OPP: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures

Why: In the large-scale disasters usually a large number of medical and non-medical staff and volunteers participate to support field operations. So far there is no unified training programme how to manage those people and to improve cooperation.

How: Creation of a minimum set of basic competencies and skills for different first aid spontaneous volunteers with a unified training program; Integration of volunteers in real field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities.

OPP: Development and testing of Joint multinational training kit for first responders.

Why: There is clear need to develop and test an advanced education and training kit for first responders focused on cross-border MCI at the European level and according to national guidelines.

How: The implementation of this opportunity will provide Joint multinational training for first responders (EMS, FRS, Police, etc.) that would serve as a basis for improvement the efficiency into MCI management. The training would include: First, knowledge and skills of the First responders from different EU MS and to be able to work together in a more effective way. Second, in addition to the knowledge on basic medical topics, the training should provide knowledge of disaster management principles (command, control, communication, coordination and collaboration). Finally, online and hands-on training would help the trainees to use the new technological solutions for digitalisation of the existing procedures and data exchange.

9. Next steps

The harmonisation framework is at the service of the project. New steps will come from needs that the project may have in the future. Also, challenges that the project faces.

On the other hand, the work in the following months will focus on the use of this OODA loop in each of the decisions that the project will take. In this way, we try to speed up the decision-making process and not stagnate any task with it.

Continue the production of key elements such as standard procedures and certification schemes.

9.1. Expected core outputs

The harmonisation and dynamic standardisation of the project should produce core elements that support the proper management of the project and in turn create initiatives for new projects in the future.

We will briefly explain each of these three elements:

- **Prioritised standards:** As a result of the analysis of existing standards, the identification of gaps and the proposal of further improvements to fill the gaps, a set of priority standards with requirements and recommendations will be provided as part of the project output.
- **Common procedures:** The technological work packages will have as output in the project to produce common procedures and guidelines to favour interoperability among emergency actors. These common procedures will be on operation, technology education and equipment.
- **Certification schemes:** Achieving certification is a lengthy process in many fields, in products, competences, accreditations or technologies. The project seeks a certification scheme within the existing legal framework that studies the feasibility of proposing and recommending modifications to streamline the certification process in different areas of the emergency.

10. Annex A – Glossary

Acronym	Description
WP	Advanced Command Post
UC	Use Case
SOPs	Standard Operational Procedures
C&C	Command and Control
EAB	External Advisory Board
EU	European Union
FAV	First Aid Vehicles
GA	Grant Agreement
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service
GIS	Geographic Information System
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MCD	Minimum Common Data
MCDT1	MCD Primary Triage
MCDT2	MCD Secondary Triage
EC	European Commission
DRMKC	Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre
SMDRM	Social Media-Driven Disaster Risk Management
GCRI	Global Conflict Risk Index
EIOS	Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources
CEM	Copernicus Emergency Management Service ⁹
UCPM	Union Civil Protection Mechanisms
MS	Member States
OODA	Observe – Orient – Decide - Act
SWOT	STR
PDCA	Plan – Do – Check - Act
EFQM	European Foundation for Quality Management
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
MCI	Multi Casualty Incident
VOSTs	Virtual Operation Support Teams
MDS	Minimum Data Set
FMS	Fleet Management System

Table 1 - Glossary